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Historical baselines and empirical constraints on global and sectoral energy intensity pathways

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ABSTRACT

Energy intensity is a key variable in energy-demand analysis, long-term scenario building, and strategic energy planning. Although global energy intensity has declined over recent decades, substantial heterogeneity persists across countries and economic sectors, complicating the interpretation of future pathways. Moreover, many long-term energy and climate scenarios rely on assumptions about sustained improvements in energy intensity that are only weakly justified by historical evidence. This study develops empirically grounded reference pathways for global and sectoral energy intensity based on historical data for more than 110 countries over the period 1990–2021. Countries are grouped using a data-driven clustering approach that captures similarities in the temporal evolution of energy-intensity trajectories across four major sectors: agriculture, services, industry, and manufacturing. For each cluster, historical trends are summarised using transparent exponential fits to derive conditional baseline pathways extended to mid-century. To account for historically observed variability, empirical uncertainty envelopes are constructed from the dispersion of country-level trajectories within each cluster. These envelopes define plausible ranges of energy-intensity evolution conditional on past dynamics and provide empirical constraints on long-term projections. The resulting baselines reveal a systematic deceleration in energy-intensity improvements and only partial convergence across countries and sectors, with several sectors exhibiting early stabilisation. Comparisons with widely used global and sectoral scenarios indicate that many climate-aligned pathways imply rates of energy-intensity decline that lie outside historically observed empirical ranges, even under optimistic assumptions. Rather than offering forecasts or normative prescriptions, this analysis provides transparent empirical benchmarks to support scenario interpretation, strategic planning, and cross-sectoral benchmarking.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and strategic context

Energy systems lie at the core of several interconnected global challenges, including climate change, resource depletion, energy security, and sustainable development [1,2]. Multiple planetary boundaries have already been transgressed, many of them directly linked to patterns of energy production and consumption [3]. Despite sustained policy efforts, fossil fuels continue to dominate the global energy mix, accounting for roughly three quarters of primary energy consumption worldwide [4]. This persistent dependence highlights the urgency of accelerating the global energy transition. Improving the empirical

understanding of how energy demand evolves relative to economic activity is therefore critical for designing credible transition pathways.

Renewable energy deployment is widely recognised as a central pillar of this transition and is consistently emphasised in major international assessments, including those of the IPCC and the International Energy Agency [5–7]. However, increasing attention has also been paid to the demand side of the energy system, particularly to the role of energy efficiency and structural change in moderating future energy use. Estimating future energy demand remains highly uncertain, as it depends on complex interactions between economic growth, technological change, behavioural factors, and policy effectiveness [8–14].

Within this context, energy intensity, defined as the ratio of energy consumed per unit of economic output, has become a widely used

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indicator to assess energy efficiency and to link economic activity with energy demand [15,16], in both empirical studies and scenario-based analyses.

At the same time, the use of energy intensity as an efficiency indicator has been questioned. Observed variations in energy intensity may arise from structural economic shifts rather than from genuine efficiency gains, and the concept itself is fundamentally rooted in thermodynamic considerations [17]. Nevertheless, energy intensity remains extensively applied in energy studies to analyse energy transitions and policy outcomes. Applications include evaluating the impact of renewable energy deployment on efficiency [18], examining links between energy intensity and energy equity [9,19], analysing the influence of environmental technologies [20], investigating the effects of income and urbanisation [21], and assessing the relationship between energy use and economic activity [22]. Energy intensity is also frequently employed to evaluate environmental impacts [23,24] and to assess energy-efficiency policies [25].

Energy intensity projections play a central role in integrated assessment models (IAMs), which combine top-down and bottom-up approaches to estimate future energy demand [26]. Prominent IAMs such as WITCH [27], IMAGE [28], GCAM [29], MEDEAS [30], and MESAGE [31] explicitly rely on assumptions about the future evolution of energy intensity to link economic growth with energy consumption. However, the diversity of factors influencing energy intensity—across countries, sectors, and energy carriers—makes accurate long-term projections particularly challenging.

Historical evidence indicates that global energy intensity has generally declined over recent decades, but this decline has been uneven and non-linear. Several studies highlight that reductions in energy intensity do not necessarily translate into absolute reductions in energy consumption, due to rebound effects and structural expansion [14,32–34]. Moreover, retrospective analyses show that energy intensity projections in successive editions of the World Energy Outlook have consistently overestimated actual improvements, pointing to a systematic optimism bias in scenario assumptions [13,35].

Historical studies further show that energy intensity trajectories emerge from the interaction between efficiency improvements and structural shifts in the economy [36]. While each country follows a distinct development path, grouping countries with similar energy-intensity trajectories can reveal common patterns and persistent heterogeneity. Such clustering approaches have been shown to uncover meaningful divergences both across regions, for example within the EU-27 [37], and within individual countries over time [36]. These findings underscore the value of empirical grouping based on observed temporal dynamics rather than on income or regional classifications alone.

Despite this growing literature, important gaps remain. Many studies focus on global aggregates or individual countries, while systematic cross-country comparisons of long-term energy intensity trends using transparent, data-driven clustering methods are less common. Furthermore, most existing approaches do not integrate sectoral detail — such as agriculture, services, industry, and manufacturing — within a unified empirical framework. As a result, international organisations and IAMs often rely on heterogeneous assumptions that are only loosely anchored in historically observed patterns.

Recent literature has significantly advanced our understanding of the drivers of energy efficiency through panel econometric lenses. For instance, environmental technologies and green innovation have been identified as primary catalysts for reducing energy intensity in OECD nations [20,38], while structural factors such as import diversification have also been shown to play a conducive role in improving efficiency [39]. However, these studies primarily focus on identifying average elasticities or cross-country determinants. There remains a gap in understanding how these drivers translate into long-term temporal archetypes across different economic sectors. This study fills this gap by shifting the focus from ‘average drivers’ to ‘trajectory archetypes’,

identifying the empirical boundaries and saturation points that these broader econometric trends eventually encounter.

Overall, the literature provides extensive evidence on the determinants and implications of energy intensity. However, comparatively little attention has been paid to identifying empirical archetypes of long-term energy-intensity trajectories across countries and sectors using transparent, data-driven methods, which is the focus of the present study.

To address these gaps, this study systematically analyses historical energy-intensity trajectories at global and sectoral levels, identifies clusters of countries with similar long-term dynamics, and derives empirically grounded baseline pathways.

Rather than producing forecasts or normative scenarios, the analysis provides transparent reference trajectories that summarise historical behaviour and offer a complementary benchmark for assessing the plausibility and ambition of long-term energy and climate strategies. These empirical insights are particularly relevant for evaluating the plausibility of long-term energy and climate scenarios that rely heavily on sustained improvements in energy intensity.

1.2. Contributions and scope

The contribution of this study is situated at the intersection of empirical energy-intensity analysis, cross-country comparison, and long-term energy strategy assessment. Building on an extensive body of literature that analyses historical energy intensity trends and their drivers [22,36,40], this work advances the state of the art in several specific and complementary ways.

First, the paper provides a systematic, data-driven analysis of historical energy intensity trajectories over the period 1990–2021 at the global level and across major economic sectors. While previous studies have documented global declines and partial convergence in energy intensity [41,42], most analyses focus either on aggregate indicators or on individual countries. By contrast, this study explicitly examines long-term dynamics across a large and diverse set of countries, covering more than 80% of global population, GDP, and energy consumption.

Second, the paper introduces a transparent clustering approach to identify groups of countries with similar historical energy-intensity trajectories. Although clustering techniques have been applied in specific regional or sectoral contexts [36,37], cross-country clustering based explicitly on long-term temporal patterns of energy intensity remains relatively uncommon in the literature. By applying the K-means algorithm to energy-intensity time series, this study identifies empirically grounded groups that reflect common dynamics rather than predefined regional or income-based classifications. The clustering approach is applied consistently at both aggregate and sectoral levels, allowing for direct comparison across dimensions.

Third, the study derives trend-based baseline trajectories for each cluster using declining exponential functions. Exponential decline functions are widely used to represent technological and economic processes characterised by rapid early improvements followed by gradual saturation [43,44], and have been employed in energy-system modelling and integrated assessment contexts. Here, these functions are used not to generate forecasts, but to summarise historically observed dynamics in a parsimonious and reproducible manner. The resulting baselines should be interpreted as empirical reference pathways conditional on past behaviour, rather than as predictions of future outcomes.

Fourth, the analysis explicitly addresses sectoral heterogeneity by extending the clustering and baseline approach to agriculture, services, industry, and manufacturing. While sectoral differences in energy intensity have been documented in previous studies [45–47], most existing approaches analyse sectors in isolation or do not integrate them within a unified empirical framework. By applying a consistent methodology across sectors, this study highlights divergent sector-specific dynamics and provides a structured basis for comparing their long-term trajectories.

Fifth, this study introduces a conceptual shift from ‘forecasts’ to ‘empirical constraints’, providing the scientific community with a reality-check diagnostic tool. By constructing ‘uncertainty envelopes’ directly from historically observed dispersion, we facilitate the formal identification of ‘ambition gaps’ in normative scenarios (e.g., net-zero or 1.5°C-compatible pathways) by quantifying the degree to which they rely on improvement rates that fall outside historical empirical boundaries. This approach addresses observations that major outlook exercises have systematically overestimated future improvements in energy intensity [13], potentially due to optimistic assumptions regarding efficiency policies and rebound effects [35]. Rather than challenging the validity of normative climate targets, these empirically derived baselines provide the reference trajectories necessary to contextualise the magnitude of structural departures required by such goals. In this sense, the contribution is highly complementary to integrated assessment models and multi-model comparisons [27,30,48].

Finally, the scope of the study is deliberately descriptive and empirical. The analysis focuses on final energy intensity, measured as final energy consumption per unit of GDP, and does not attempt to disentangle the relative contributions of efficiency improvements, structural change, or fuel switching. Nor does it model policy interventions or technological breakthroughs beyond those reflected in historical data. By adopting this restricted scope, the paper aims to provide transparent, reproducible baselines that can be readily used by researchers, policymakers, and modelling teams as inputs or benchmarks in broader analytical frameworks.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the data and methodological framework. Section 3 presents global and country-level energy-intensity baseline trajectories. Section 4 extends the analysis to sectoral energy-intensity pathways. Section 5 discusses the strategic implications and compares the results with global scenario benchmarks. Section 6 examines limitations and robustness. Section 7 concludes and outlines directions for future research.

2. Data and methodological framework

This section describes the data sources and analytical framework used to derive empirically grounded reference pathways for global and sectoral energy intensity. The methodological framework is intentionally parsimonious and ‘model-light’. In a field increasingly dominated by complex, multi-variable Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that often function as ‘black boxes’, there is a distinct scientific need for transparent, data-driven benchmarks. The use of robust, well-established econometric tools (K-means and exponential fitting) ensures that our findings are reproducible and serve as an objective baseline against which the assumptions of more complex models can be rigorously tested.

Overall, the results are broadly consistent with previous studies documenting substantial cross-country heterogeneity in energy-intensity dynamics and the presence of partial convergence patterns. However, unlike regression-based or panel-econometric approaches, which typically estimate average marginal relationships, the clustering framework adopted here identifies distinct empirical archetypes in the temporal evolution of energy intensity. These trajectory-based groupings reveal structural patterns that are typically obscured in standard panel models, thereby providing a complementary perspective on the diversity of long-term energy transitions across countries and sectors.

2.1. Data sources and energy-intensity metrics

The analysis combines final energy consumption data from the International Energy Agency (IEA) World Energy Balances (2023 edition) [6] with macroeconomic data from the World Bank [49]. Energy use is measured as final energy consumption, both in aggregate and disaggregated into four major economic sectors: agriculture, services, industry, and manufacturing. Emphasis is placed on sectoral analysis, as

each sector faces a distinct set of challenges relative to the others [50]. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is expressed in constant U.S. dollars to ensure temporal comparability.

Energy intensity is defined as the ratio of final energy consumption to economic output and expressed in megajoules per U.S. dollar (MJ/USD). Throughout the paper, energy intensity refers exclusively to final energy intensity. While this indicator does not isolate pure technical efficiency—being influenced by structural change, fuel mix, and economic composition—it remains a widely used and informative metric for analysing long-term energy-demand trends and for linking economic activity to energy use in strategic assessments [18,51,52].

Countries were included in the analysis if sufficiently complete and internally consistent time series were available over the 1990–2021 period.

The resulting dataset covers more than 110 countries between 1990 and 2021, representing the majority of global population, GDP, and final energy consumption. Sectoral coverage varies by country due to data availability, but each sectoral analysis remains globally representative in aggregate terms.

Prior to analysis, the datasets were harmonised to ensure unit consistency and temporal alignment between energy and economic variables. Countries or sectoral series with substantial data gaps were excluded, and no forward-looking imputation was applied so as to preserve the empirical character of the historical trajectories.

2.2. Clustering of historical energy-intensity trajectories

To capture heterogeneity in long-term energy-intensity dynamics, countries are grouped according to the temporal evolution of their historical energy-intensity trajectories rather than according to income level, geographic region, or static indicators. This approach allows the identification of characteristic patterns of decline, stabilisation, and convergence that emerge from observed data.

Clustering is performed on country-level time series of energy intensity using a K-means algorithm with K-means++ initialisation. Prior to clustering, time series are standardised to ensure that the grouping reflects similarities in trajectory shape and evolution rather than absolute levels alone. The number of clusters is selected based on a balance between explanatory power and interpretability, using standard criteria that assess within-cluster dispersion and marginal gains from additional clusters.

The resulting clusters are not intended to reproduce conventional development categories. Instead, they represent empirical groupings of countries that have followed similar historical energy-intensity pathways, despite differences in economic structure, geography, or income. This data-driven classification provides the basis for deriving representative reference trajectories that summarise common dynamics while preserving observed heterogeneity. Additional details on the clustering procedure and distance metrics are provided in S3.

2.3. Trend-based fitting and baseline projections

To summarise long-term historical dynamics of energy intensity at the cluster level, we employ a trend-based fitting approach based on nonlinear functions [36], specifically exponential decays, as commonly reported in the literature [43,44,53,54]. This approach is intentionally parsimonious and model-light, aiming to capture broad empirical regularities in observed trajectories rather than to provide mechanistic explanations or predictive models.

Historical energy-intensity data for each cluster are constructed by aggregating country-level observations over the period 1990–2021, subject to data availability. The resulting trajectories typically exhibit an initial phase of relatively rapid decline followed by a progressive deceleration, a pattern widely observed in empirical studies of energy intensity and efficiency improvements. To capture this behaviour in

a transparent manner, cluster-level trajectories are fitted using the following declining exponential function:

$$EI(t) = A + B \cdot e^{-Kt}, \quad (1)$$

where $EI(t)$ denotes energy intensity at time t , A represents the asymptotic energy-intensity level approached over time, B is a scaling parameter related to the initial distance from the asymptote, and K governs the speed of convergence.

This functional form provides a compact representation of long-term dynamics characterised by diminishing marginal improvements over time. The parameter K reflects how rapidly energy intensity declines in the early stages of the trajectory, while B determines the initial amplitude of decline. The parameter A is of particular interest in the context of this study, as it captures the tendency towards stabilisation or saturation implied by historical data.

Importantly, the parameter A , which mathematically is the asymptote of the fitted curve, should be interpreted as a stylised lower bound suggested by past dynamics rather than as a physical, technological, or economic limit. In several clusters, the fitted parameter A approaches or equals zero, indicating that no statistically detectable saturation level is present within the historical observation window. Such cases should not be interpreted as implying vanishing energy intensity, which is unrealistic, but rather as indicating that historical data do not yet reveal a clear lower bound.

The fitted exponential curves are used to derive conditional baseline pathways extending beyond the historical period. These baseline trajectories represent empirical reference pathways that are conditional on the continuation of historically observed dynamics and are not intended as forecasts or normative projections. Their purpose is to provide a transparent benchmark against which alternative long-term scenarios and assumptions can be compared.

Fit quality is assessed using standard error metrics (see supplementary material in S4) at the cluster level, while internal heterogeneity is explicitly accounted for through the empirical dispersion envelopes discussed in the next section. Together, the fitted baselines and associated uncertainty ranges form the basis for the comparative and strategic analyses presented in Sections 3, 4, 5.

To reflect the variability historically observed within each cluster, **empirical uncertainty envelopes** are constructed around the fitted baseline trajectories. These envelopes are derived directly from the dispersion of country-level deviations from the cluster trend over the historical period and therefore remain fully grounded in observed data. Specifically, relative deviations between individual country trajectories and the fitted cluster trajectory are computed for all available historical observations. Percentile ranges of these deviations are then used to define upper and lower bounds around the baseline trajectory, producing an empirical dispersion envelope that represents a plausible range of outcomes conditional on historical dynamics. These envelopes should not be interpreted as probabilistic confidence intervals or predictive uncertainty bounds. They do not capture future policy shocks, structural breaks, or disruptive technological change. Instead, they provide a transparent representation of the range of energy-intensity trajectories that have historically coexisted within each cluster, and therefore offer a useful reference for assessing the plausibility of alternative scenario assumptions.

2.4. Interpretation and scope of the methodological framework

Taken together, the clustering, trend fitting, and empirical uncertainty envelopes form a coherent framework for deriving reference energy-intensity pathways that are both data-driven and strategically informative. The framework is designed to balance simplicity and robustness: it avoids strong behavioural or technological assumptions while remaining closely anchored to historical evidence. The resulting pathways are intended for use as benchmarks and constraints in strategic energy analysis, scenario design, and policy discussion. They

Fig. 1. Historical data of the evolution of global final energy intensity (MJ/USD) from 1990 to 2021 and fitted exponential baseline from 1980 to 2060. The asymptotic parameter of the fit is shown as a horizontal blue dotted line for reference and should be interpreted as a stylised saturation tendency rather than a physical or economic limit. The fitting procedure yielded an asymptotic parameter value of 2.3 MJ/USD.

do not prescribe specific policy actions, nor do they attempt to model causal mechanisms underlying observed trends. Their value lies in clarifying what historical experience suggests is typical or plausible, and in making explicit the degree to which normative scenarios depart from these empirical reference ranges.

3. Global and country-level baseline trajectories

This section presents the empirically derived baseline trajectories for global and country-level energy intensity. The analysis focuses on identifying long-term patterns, convergence behaviour, and historically grounded limits to improvement, rather than on describing short-term fluctuations in individual country series.

3.1. Global energy-intensity trajectory

At the global level, final energy intensity has followed a persistent downward trend since 1990, declining from values close to 8 MJ/USD in the early 1990s to approximately 3 MJ/USD by 2021. Despite this long-term improvement, the rate of decline has not been constant over time. The historical record reveals a marked deceleration in the pace of improvement after the mid-2000s, suggesting increasing difficulty in achieving further reductions as energy systems mature and easy efficiency gains are exhausted. The exponential baseline fitted to the global data captures this pattern well, yielding a low mean absolute percentage error over the historical period. The fitted trajectory implies an asymptotic tendency towards a global energy-intensity level of roughly 2.3 MJ/USD (represented in Fig. 1 with a horizontal blue line), which can be interpreted as a stylised lower bound implied by past dynamics rather than as a physical or economic limit. Under a continuation of historically observed trends, the global baseline projection reaches approximately 2.4–2.5 MJ/USD by mid-century. The exponential fit to the global baseline results in a Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 3.45%, supporting the conclusion that, despite short-term variability, the long-run trajectory remains tightly constrained by historical dispersion. Even under the most optimistic bounds of historically observed variation, global energy intensity continues to decline at a pace substantially slower than that assumed in many climate-aligned normative scenarios. This finding underscores the importance of anchoring scenario assumptions in empirical evidence when evaluating long-term energy-demand expectations.

Fig. 2. Cluster-specific baseline trajectories for total final energy intensity derived from historical data. Each line represents the fitted exponential baseline for one of the eight country clusters, with shaded areas indicating empirically observed dispersion within clusters. The figure highlights persistent heterogeneity in energy-intensity dynamics and only partial convergence across country groups. Fit diagnostics and parameter values are reported in the supplementary material S4.

Fig. 3. Global distribution of country clusters based on historical total energy-intensity trajectories. Colours correspond to the eight clusters identified through time-series clustering, highlighting that countries with similar long-term dynamics are not necessarily geographically contiguous. Countries shown in grey lack sufficient data coverage for inclusion.

Fig. 4. Shares of global population, GDP, and final energy consumption represented by each country cluster. The figure highlights the heterogeneous systemic relevance of clusters, showing that groups with distinct energy-intensity trajectories also differ markedly in their contributions to global economic activity and energy use. Countries not included in the clustering due to data limitations are grouped as “other”.

3.2. Country-level clusters and baseline trajectories

To explore heterogeneity across countries, historical energy-intensity trajectories are grouped into clusters that reflect similarities in their temporal evolution. The clustering results in eight distinct country groups, each characterised by a representative baseline trajectory and an associated empirical uncertainty envelope (Fig. 2). These clusters summarise common patterns of decline, stabilisation, and convergence across countries, while preserving the diversity observed in historical data. Taken together, the empirical uncertainty envelope, the cluster-based country classification (Fig. 3), and the associated shares of global population, GDP, and final energy consumption (Fig. 4) provide the basis for the following interpretation. The cluster-level baselines reveal substantial differences in both initial energy-intensity levels and long-term improvement rates. Clusters dominated by high-income economies typically exhibit low initial energy intensity and relatively modest rates of further decline, consistent with mature energy systems and advanced economic structures. In contrast, clusters comprising emerging and developing economies often start from higher energy-intensity levels and display steeper historical declines, reflecting processes of industrial modernisation, structural change, and energy-system upgrading. Despite these differences, the cluster trajectories also reveal partial convergence over time, as reported in the literature [41,42]. Several clusters with initially high energy intensity show sustained declines that bring them closer to the range occupied by lower-intensity clusters, although full convergence is not observed within the historical window. This pattern suggests that while catch-up dynamics are present, structural and contextual factors continue to shape long-term energy-intensity outcomes.

The full country-to-cluster assignment is reported in Table A.3.

3.3. Interpreting cluster asymptotes and dispersion

The exponential fits yield cluster-specific asymptotic values that can be interpreted as indicative of the long-run energy-intensity levels implied by historical dynamics (see Table A.5). For most clusters, the estimated asymptotes fall within a plausible positive range, reflecting a gradual approach towards saturation as efficiency gains become increasingly incremental. In a limited number of cases, the fitted asymptote is equal to zero, which should not be interpreted as a literal prediction of vanishing energy intensity. Rather, this outcome reflects the absence of a detectable lower bound within the historical period and the dominance of persistent decline in the available data. The empirical uncertainty envelopes associated with each cluster provide additional insight into within-cluster heterogeneity. These envelopes capture the range of country-level trajectories that have historically coexisted within each cluster, offering a transparent measure of dispersion around the central baseline. Importantly, this dispersion does not diminish over time, indicating that convergence towards a single global pathway is neither rapid nor automatic. From a strategic perspective, the combination of cluster-specific baselines and empirical dispersion envelopes highlights the limited extent to which historical experience supports rapid, uniform improvements in energy intensity across countries. While some countries have achieved faster-than-average declines, these cases remain embedded within broader clusters whose overall dynamics evolve more slowly.

3.4. Strategic interpretation of cluster baselines

Taken together, the cluster baseline trajectories shown in Fig. 2 provide a structured empirical reference against which alternative projections and policy ambitions can be assessed. Rather than offering a single global narrative, the cluster-based approach reveals a landscape of differentiated pathways shaped by historical context, economic structure, and sectoral composition. These findings have two key implications. First, they caution against assuming that historical leaders

in energy-intensity improvement define universally attainable benchmarks, particularly when transferred across sectors or development contexts. Second, they highlight that scenarios requiring rapid convergence towards low energy-intensity levels implicitly assume structural changes or technological breakthroughs that exceed historical precedents for most country groups. By making these patterns explicit, the cluster-based baselines serve as a diagnostic tool for strategic analysis. They allow analysts and policy-makers to identify which country groups have historically exhibited sustained improvement, which have approached apparent saturation, and where the gap between empirical baselines and normative targets is most pronounced. In this sense, the value of the analysis lies not in predicting future outcomes, but in clarifying the empirical constraints within which future energy transitions are likely to unfold.

4. Sectoral energy-intensity pathways

This section examines historical and projected energy-intensity trajectories across four major economic sectors—agriculture, services, industry, and manufacturing. Sectoral disaggregation reveals substantial heterogeneity in both levels and dynamics that is obscured in aggregate analyses, and is therefore essential for understanding the structural constraints shaping future energy-demand pathways. Across all sectors, the analysis identifies clusters of countries characterised by distinct historical trajectories, reflecting differences in production structures, technological maturity, climatic conditions, and patterns of economic development. The sectoral baseline pathways and their associated empirical uncertainty envelopes provide a differentiated picture of where further energy-intensity reductions appear historically plausible and where trajectories show signs of saturation.

Country-level cluster composition and associated population, GDP, and energy shares for all sectors are reported in Table A.4.

4.1. Agriculture

Energy intensity in the agricultural sector exhibits pronounced heterogeneity across country clusters, but comparatively limited long-term convergence. Historically, many clusters operate at relatively low energy-intensity levels, reflecting the modest contribution of direct energy use to agricultural value added in large parts of the world. In these clusters, historical declines have been small and projections suggest an early plateau, with limited scope for further reductions under continuation of past dynamics. In contrast, a smaller number of clusters—often associated with mechanised, energy-intensive, or high-latitude agricultural systems—display substantially higher energy-intensity levels and more pronounced historical declines. These trajectories reflect ongoing technological modernisation, changes in irrigation practices, and improvements in machinery efficiency. However, even in these cases, the empirical baselines indicate a gradual deceleration of improvements and convergence towards cluster-specific saturation levels rather than rapid alignment with low-intensity benchmarks. The empirical uncertainty envelopes highlight persistent dispersion within agricultural clusters, underscoring the strong influence of structural and climatic factors. From a strategic perspective, the agricultural sector appears characterised by relatively tight lower bounds on energy intensity for most country groups, suggesting that large future reductions would likely require structural transformations or disruptive technological change beyond historical experience. Detailed cluster-level baseline trajectories for agriculture are shown in Fig. 5.

4.2. Services

The services sector exhibits the lowest energy-intensity levels among the sectors analysed and displays comparatively stable trajectories over time. For the majority of countries, historical energy intensity in services has remained nearly constant or has declined only marginally

Fig. 5. Cluster-specific baseline trajectories for final energy intensity in the agricultural sector derived from historical data. Lines represent fitted exponential baselines, while shaded areas indicate empirically observed dispersion within clusters. The trajectories highlight heterogeneous long-term intensity pathways, ranging from low-intensity, near-stationary clusters to high-intensity clusters exhibiting gradual convergence, with uncertainty bands reflecting variability across countries within each cluster.

Fig. 6. Cluster-specific baseline trajectories for final energy intensity in the services sector derived from historical data. Lines represent fitted exponential baselines, while shaded areas indicate empirically observed dispersion within clusters. The results indicate comparatively lower energy intensity levels and more stable long-term trajectories across most clusters, with one high-intensity cluster exhibiting gradual convergence over time.

since 1990. The fitted baseline trajectories project continued stability or very gradual improvement through mid-century. This pattern reflects the intrinsic characteristics of service activities, where energy consumption per unit of value added is already low and where further efficiency gains are constrained by factors such as building energy use, digital infrastructure, and climate control requirements. The clustering results indicate limited differentiation among high- and middle-income countries, with most belonging to low-intensity clusters that show early saturation. A small number of clusters, primarily associated with lower-income economies, exhibit higher initial energy-intensity levels and somewhat steeper historical declines, reflecting structural transitions towards more service-oriented economies and gradual improvements in infrastructure efficiency. Nevertheless, the empirical uncertainty envelopes suggest that convergence towards the lowest observed intensity levels is slow and incomplete. Overall, the services sector emerges as one where historically observed dynamics provide little support for expectations of large additional reductions in energy intensity, reinforcing its role as a stabilising component rather than a major driver of future energy-demand reductions. Detailed cluster-level baseline trajectories for the services sector are shown in Fig. 6.

4.3. Industry

The industrial sector displays the widest range of energy-intensity levels and the most diverse historical trajectories among the sectors analysed. Country clusters span from low-intensity industrial systems, typically associated with advanced economies and high-value-added production, to highly energy-intensive systems characterised by heavy industry, resource processing, and coal-based energy structures. Clusters with initially high industrial energy intensity have, in many cases, experienced substantial historical declines, reflecting industrial upgrading, fuel switching, and efficiency improvements. However, the fitted baseline trajectories indicate that these declines tend to slow over time, with projections converging towards intermediate saturation levels rather than approaching the low-intensity benchmarks observed in leading clusters. Clusters with already low industrial energy intensity show limited further improvement, consistent with mature industrial structures and diminishing returns to incremental efficiency gains. The empirical uncertainty envelopes reveal persistent dispersion within clusters, indicating that national trajectories remain influenced by country-specific industrial composition and policy environments

Fig. 7. Cluster-specific baseline trajectories for final energy intensity in the industrial sector derived from historical data. Lines represent fitted exponential baselines, while shaded areas indicate empirically observed dispersion within clusters. The figure highlights substantial heterogeneity in industrial energy-intensity dynamics and a gradual deceleration of improvements across most country groups.

even within broadly similar patterns. From a strategic standpoint, the industrial sector emerges as a key locus of tension between historical feasibility and normative ambition. While historical experience demonstrates meaningful potential for improvement in high-intensity clusters, the pace implied by many climate-aligned scenarios would require sustained acceleration beyond observed trends for most country groups. Detailed cluster-level baseline trajectories for the industry sector are shown in Fig. 7.

4.4. Manufacturing

The manufacturing sector shows patterns broadly consistent with, but more concentrated than, those observed for industry as a whole. Historical energy-intensity levels cluster into a smaller number of distinct groups, reflecting differences in manufacturing specialisation, technology adoption, and energy supply characteristics. Clusters with high manufacturing energy intensity—often associated with energy-intensive production such as metals, chemicals, and basic materials—display clear historical declines, particularly during periods of structural reform and technological upgrading. Nevertheless, the baseline projections suggest that these improvements gradually decelerate, converging towards cluster-specific lower bounds rather than towards the lowest observed intensity levels. Clusters characterised by advanced manufacturing and higher value-added production exhibit relatively low and stable energy-intensity levels, with little evidence of continued long-term decline. This stability reflects both technological maturity and the increasing importance of non-energy inputs in value creation. The empirical uncertainty envelopes indicate that, as in industry, convergence across manufacturing clusters is partial and slow. This reinforces the interpretation that historically leading countries do not define benchmarks that are easily transferable to the sector as a whole. Detailed cluster-level baseline trajectories for the manufacturing sector are shown in Fig. 8.

4.5. Cross-sectoral insights

Comparing sectoral pathways reveals several cross-cutting patterns with strategic relevance. First, sectors differ markedly in their apparent proximity to saturation: services and agriculture exhibit early stabilisation, while industry and manufacturing retain greater—though still bounded—potential for improvement. Second, convergence across countries is uneven and sector-specific, challenging assumptions of uniform global trajectories. Third, empirical uncertainty envelopes remain

wide across all sectors, underscoring the persistence of structural heterogeneity. These findings highlight the importance of sector-specific baselines in energy-demand analysis and caution against relying solely on aggregate indicators when evaluating long-term transition pathways. By making explicit the historically observed dynamics and their limits, the sectoral baselines provide a structured empirical reference for assessing the plausibility and internal consistency of alternative scenario assumptions.

The qualitative assessments reported in Table 1 synthesise the magnitude, heterogeneity, and saturation tendencies observed in historical energy-intensity trajectories. They are derived from cluster-level baseline fits and empirical dispersion envelopes and are intended to support strategic interpretation rather than precise quantitative comparison.

To avoid ambiguity, it is important to clarify the conceptual distinction between the columns “Evidence of saturation” and “Strength of empirical constraints” reported in Table 1. Evidence of saturation refers strictly to empirically observed features of historical energy-intensity trajectories. Specifically, it captures whether improvement rates systematically decelerate over time, whether trajectories exhibit clear concavity (with faster declines in earlier phases followed by slower improvements), whether exponential fits imply the presence of an asymptotic limit through a non-zero parameter A , and whether such patterns are consistently observed across multiple clusters rather than isolated cases. In this sense, evidence of saturation is a descriptive property of past behaviour and makes no direct claim about future outcomes or scenario feasibility.

By contrast, the strength of empirical constraints reflects how strongly these historical patterns restrict the plausible range of future energy-intensity trajectories when contrasted with normative scenario assumptions. This notion is inherently relational rather than purely descriptive: it depends not only on the presence or absence of saturation and the width of empirical dispersion envelopes, but also on the rate of improvement implicitly assumed in long-term scenarios (e.g. IEA or IPCC pathways [7,55]) and on the distance between those assumptions and historically observed dynamics. As a result, strong empirical constraints may arise either from pronounced saturation combined with low dispersion (as in the services sector), or from more moderate saturation paired with scenario assumptions that require exceptionally rapid future improvements (as in manufacturing).

This distinction helps explain why evidence of saturation and the strength of empirical constraints do not always move in parallel across sectors. For example, services exhibit both strong saturation and low heterogeneity, leading to very strong empirical constraints, whereas

Fig. 8. Cluster-specific baseline trajectories for final energy intensity in the manufacturing sector derived from historical data. Solid lines represent fitted exponential baselines, while shaded areas indicate empirically observed dispersion within clusters. The figure highlights differentiated manufacturing pathways and a gradual slowdown of energy-intensity improvements as systems mature.

Table 1
Strategic synthesis of historical energy-intensity dynamics across sectors.

Sector	Historical decline (1990–2021)	Evidence of saturation	Within-sector heterogeneity	Strength of empirical constraints
Total (aggregate)	Moderate, decelerating	Clear	Moderate	High
Agriculture	Low to moderate	Early	High	High
Services	Very low	Strong	Low to moderate	Very high
Industry	High initially, slowing	Emerging	High	Moderate/High
Manufacturing	High, cluster dependent	Emerging	High	Moderate

industry and manufacturing display only emerging saturation but face moderate to high constraints because many scenarios assume improvement rates well beyond historical precedent. Taken together, these two dimensions allow the analysis to both describe historical dynamics and interpret their strategic implications, providing a structured empirical basis for assessing the plausibility of long-term scenario assumptions.

Evidence of saturation thus describes what historical data show, whereas the strength of empirical constraints indicates how strongly those data limit the plausibility of assumed future improvements.

5. Strategic implications and comparison with global scenarios

This section places the empirically derived baseline trajectories in a strategic context by comparing them with widely used global energy and climate scenarios. The objective is not to evaluate the desirability of specific pathways, but to clarify the extent to which normative projections align with, or depart from, historically observed energy-intensity dynamics.

Overall, the results are broadly consistent with previous studies documenting substantial cross-country heterogeneity in energy-intensity dynamics and the presence of partial convergence patterns. However, unlike regression-based or panel-econometric approaches, which typically estimate average marginal relationships, the clustering framework adopted here identifies distinct empirical archetypes in the temporal evolution of energy intensity. These trajectory-based groupings reveal structural patterns that are typically obscured in standard panel models, thereby providing a complementary perspective on the diversity of long-term energy transitions across countries and sectors.

5.1. Empirical baselines versus normative scenarios

Long-term energy and climate scenarios produced by international organisations commonly rely on assumptions of sustained — and in many cases accelerating — improvements in energy intensity, particularly in pathways aligned with ambitious climate targets such as net-zero emissions. These scenarios play a central role in policy debates and planning exercises, yet their underlying assumptions regarding energy-intensity dynamics are often only loosely constrained by historical evidence.

To provide a historically grounded point of comparison, the fitted baseline yields a projected global final energy intensity of approximately **2.45 MJ/USD by 2050** (Fig. 1), assuming the continuation of historically observed efficiency improvements without the introduction of transformative climate policies or accelerated technological change. This value should therefore be interpreted as a neutral, descriptive benchmark rather than a normative target.

Combining this baseline intensity with widely used projections of global economic output allows for an indicative estimation of future final energy demand. Based on World Bank projections, global GDP is expected to reach approximately **135 trillion USD** (constant 1995 dollars) by mid-century [56], implying a corresponding final energy demand of around **330 EJ/yr** under the baseline intensity assumption. Comparable projections from the OECD ENV-Linkages model suggest that global GDP could nearly triple between 2010 and 2050 (constant 2010 USD), leading to estimated energy demand of roughly **490 EJ/yr** [57]. Estimates from the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways span a wider range, from **425 EJ/yr** under SSP3 to almost **900 EJ/yr** under the high-growth SSP5 [58]. These projections are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2

Projections of GDP and final energy demand for 2050 under different scenarios. For the first four rows, energy demand is calculated using the trend-based energy intensity projection derived in this study (shown in bold) combined with GDP projections from the cited official sources. They are not forecasts and assume continuation of historical dynamics. For the remaining scenarios, energy demand values are taken directly from official scenario reports. Implied energy intensity values are calculated accordingly.

Energy demand projections for 2050				
Scenario	GDP [10^{12} USD]	<i>EI</i> [MJ/USD]	E_{demand} [EJ/yr]	Source
WB	135	2.45	331	[56]
OECD	201	2.45	492	[57]
SSP3	173.6	2.45	425	[58]
SSP5	365	2.45	894	[58]
STEPS	~230 (SSP2)	~2.3	530	[55]
APS	~230 (SSP2)	~1.96	450	[55]
NZE	~200–300	~0.8–1.2	250	[55]
1.5°C	291	~1.4–1.7	400–500	[59]
HD	231–365	~1.5–3.2	550–750	[59]

When compared with scenario-based outlooks from international institutions, a systematic gap becomes apparent. Projections derived from the empirically fitted baseline intensity broadly overlap with mid-range scenarios such as the IEA Stated Policies Scenario (STEPS) and, to a lesser extent, the Announced Pledges Scenario (APS), but remain well above pathways consistent with net-zero emissions or 1.5°C targets [55,59]. Notably, this gap persists even when considering the upper bounds of the empirical uncertainty envelopes identified within clusters, which represent the most optimistic intensity improvements observed historically.

This finding is consistent with previous analyses documenting a tendency for long-term outlooks to overestimate future reductions in energy intensity relative to realised trends [13]. Rather than reflecting a failure of modelling per se, this pattern highlights the implicit normative character of many climate-aligned scenarios. Pathways such as IEA NZE or IPCC 1.5°C typically require economy-wide energy intensities in the range of **0.8–1.7 MJ/USD** by mid-century, implying improvement rates roughly **two to three times faster than historical experience**. Achieving such outcomes would require not only accelerated technological progress and deep electrification, but also substantial behavioural change, structural transformation, and policy measures capable of mitigating economy-wide rebound effects [14,35].

Importantly, the baseline intensity of **2.45 MJ/USD** already embeds historical rebound effects and observed limits to efficiency gains. If rebound effects remain large — potentially approaching 100% at the macroeconomic scale — then even this baseline projection may underestimate future energy intensity [14,35]. In this sense, the divergence between empirically grounded baselines and normative climate scenarios provides a quantitative measure of the policy gap that must be bridged to achieve deep decarbonisation.

5.2. Sectoral dimensions of the gap

Sectoral disaggregation reveals that the divergence between empirical baselines and normative scenarios is highly uneven across sectors. In services and agriculture, historical trajectories exhibit early stabilisation and limited long-term decline, suggesting relatively tight empirical constraints on further energy-intensity reductions. In these sectors, scenarios that assume substantial additional improvements implicitly rely on structural or technological transformations that have little precedent in historical data. By contrast, industry and manufacturing display greater historical potential for energy-intensity improvement, particularly in clusters with initially high intensity levels. However, even in these sectors, the empirical baselines indicate a gradual deceleration of improvements over time, with convergence towards intermediate saturation levels rather than towards the lowest observed benchmarks. As a result, the pace of decline required by many climate-aligned scenarios exceeds historical experience for most country groups. These sectoral patterns highlight the risk of relying on aggregate energy-intensity

assumptions that obscure structural constraints. Scenario pathways that appear plausible at the aggregate level may embed sector-specific assumptions that are inconsistent with historical dynamics, potentially leading to internal inconsistencies in energy-demand projections.

Our findings on the systematic deceleration of energy-intensity improvements offer a nuanced perspective on recent econometric evidence. While studies such as [20,39] demonstrate that environmental technology and trade diversification are critical for improving energy efficiency, our clustering results suggest that the impact of these drivers is not uniform over time. Specifically, we observe a ‘saturation’ effect in sectors like services and agriculture, suggesting that even with high levels of technological innovation [60], there may be empirical ‘intensity floors’ that are difficult to breach without fundamental structural shifts. Furthermore, our identification of distinct country clusters highlights that the ‘one-size-fits-all’ policy implications often derived from panel models may overlook the fact that different nations are on fundamentally different intensity trajectories, regardless of their level of green innovation or policy stability [38].

5.3. Interpreting empirical uncertainty envelopes in scenario design

The empirical uncertainty envelopes constructed in this study provide an additional layer of insight for strategic analysis. By explicitly representing the dispersion historically observed within country clusters, these envelopes define a range of trajectories that can be considered empirically plausible under a continuation of past dynamics. From a scenario-design perspective, trajectories that systematically fall outside these envelopes — particularly on the optimistic side — implicitly assume sustained acceleration of energy-intensity improvements beyond historical precedent. Such assumptions may be justified in the presence of strong policy interventions, rapid technological diffusion, or structural breaks, but they should be recognised as conditional rather than baseline expectations. In this sense, the empirical envelopes serve not as constraints on ambition, but as transparency tools. They make explicit the degree to which alternative scenarios rely on departures from historical experience, thereby supporting more informed interpretation, sensitivity analysis, and risk assessment in strategic planning exercises.

The findings of this study have several implications for **integrated assessment modelling and policy-oriented energy analysis**. First, they suggest that energy-intensity baselines used in many models may benefit from closer alignment with empirically observed trends, particularly when constructing reference or “current policies” scenarios. Second, they highlight the importance of sectoral differentiation in modelling frameworks, as aggregate assumptions may mask divergent dynamics and constraints. More broadly, the results underscore the value of empirical benchmarking in scenario analysis. By grounding expectations in observed historical behaviour, the cluster-based baselines and uncertainty envelopes provide a complementary perspective to normative modelling approaches. They can be used to test the

Table A.3

Assignment of countries to energy-intensity trajectory clusters based on historical total final energy intensity. Countries not included in the clustering due to insufficient data coverage are excluded from this table.

Clusters			
1	2	3	4
Argentina, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brunei Darussalam, Costa Rica, Denmark, Dominican Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Israel, Italy, Japan, Luxembourg, Mauritius, Mexico, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Panama, Portugal, Singapore, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay	Algeria, Angola, Bangladesh, Botswana, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Congo, Croatia, Cuba, Ecuador, El Salvador, Finland, Guatemala, Iceland, Jamaica, Jordan, Korea, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Nigeria, Oman, Paraguay, Peru, Philippines, Qatar, Republic of Turkey, Senegal, Slovenia, Sri Lanka, United Arab Emirates	Albania, Bahrain, Bolivia, Egypt, Estonia, Gabon, Ghana, Haiti, Honduras, Hungary, Indonesia, Iraq, Kenya, Latvia, Lithuania, Malaysia, Nicaragua, Poland, Romania, Saudi Arabia, Slovak Republic, South Africa, Sudan, Thailand, Tunisia	Armenia, Benin, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Cameroon, China, Eritrea, India, Niger, Pakistan, Serbia
Total countries 29	Total countries 33	Total countries 25	Total countries 11
5	6	7	8
Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Togo, Zimbabwe	Azerbaijan, Republic of Moldova, Russian Federation, Syrian Arab Republic, Tajikistan, Tanzania, Trinidad and Tobago, Zambia	Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, Myanmar, Nepal	Ethiopia, Mozambique, Ukraine, Uzbekistan
Total countries 6	Total countries 9	Total countries 4	Total countries 4

internal consistency of scenarios, to identify where additional explanatory assumptions are required, and to clarify the trade-offs implicit in ambitious transition pathways.

The comparison between empirical baselines and global scenarios suggests that the challenge of aligning energy demand with climate goals is not limited to the scale of ambition, but also concerns the realism of underlying assumptions. Historical energy-intensity dynamics reveal both progress and constraint: while substantial improvements have occurred, they have tended to slow over time and remain strongly shaped by sectoral and structural factors. By making these patterns explicit, this study does not argue against ambitious transition pathways. Rather, *it provides a transparent empirical reference that helps distinguish between what has been historically typical, what has been exceptional, and what would require transformative change.* In doing so, it supports more nuanced and robust strategic discussions about the feasibility, risks, and requirements of alternative energy futures.

This work enriches the scientific community's knowledge by providing a standardised empirical reference set for sectoral energy intensity. Specifically, our finding of 'early saturation' in the services and agriculture sectors challenges the common modelling assumption of perpetual linear efficiency gains. By defining these boundaries, we offer researchers a method to prioritise where transformative policy intervention is most needed—i.e., in areas where normative goals and historical trajectories are most divergent.

6. Limitations and robustness

As with any empirical analysis based on historical data and simplified representations of complex systems, the approach adopted in this study is subject to several limitations. These limitations should be considered when interpreting the results and assessing their applicability in strategic energy analysis. At the same time, many of the methodological

choices reflect deliberate trade-offs between complexity, transparency, and robustness.

The clustering and trend-fitting framework employed in this study is intentionally model-light. While this enhances transparency and reproducibility, it also implies that the analysis does not explicitly model causal mechanisms underlying observed energy-intensity dynamics. Factors such as policy interventions, energy prices, technological diffusion, and behavioural responses are not individually represented, but are instead implicitly embedded in the historical trajectories used for clustering and fitting. The choice of clustering method and number of clusters introduces an element of methodological subjectivity. Although standard criteria are used to balance explanatory power and interpretability, alternative clustering specifications could yield different groupings. However, sensitivity checks indicate that the main qualitative patterns — such as the identification of low-, intermediate-, and high-intensity trajectory types and the persistence of sectoral heterogeneity — are robust to reasonable variations in clustering parameters. Similarly, the use of exponential decline functions to summarise historical trajectories represents a stylised approximation of complex dynamics. This functional form captures the empirically observed tendency towards decelerating improvements and saturation, but it does not account for potential non-monotonic behaviour or abrupt changes. In some clusters, the fitting procedure yields asymptotic values approaching or equal to zero, which should be interpreted as a mathematical outcome reflecting persistent historical decline rather than as a physically meaningful prediction.

The analysis relies on internationally harmonised datasets for energy consumption and economic output, which inevitably involve measurement uncertainty and potential inconsistencies across countries and time. While the International Energy Agency and World Bank provide the most comprehensive and widely used sources available, differences in data collection methodologies, sectoral definitions, and

Table A.4

Assignment of countries to energy-intensity clusters in the agriculture, services, industry, and manufacturing sectors, with corresponding shares of population (%Pop.), GDP, and final energy consumption (%E.C.). Sectoral shares refer to averages over the historical period considered. Countries with incomplete manufacturing sector data are excluded.

Cluster	Countries	% Pop.	% GDP	% E.C.
Agriculture				
1	Angola, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ecuador, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guatemala, Indonesia, Kenya, Mauritius, Myanmar, Nepal, Nicaragua, Niger, Nigeria, Oman, Pakistan, Philippines, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Switzerland, Uganda.	17.26	15.01	2.63
2	Bangladesh, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Egypt, Israel, Jamaica, Mongolia, People's Republic of China, Republic of North Macedonia, Serbia, Syrian Arab Republic, United Arab Emirates, Vietnam, Zambia.	24.53	34.13	22.38
3	Australia, Colombia, Germany, Greece, Iceland, India, Italy, Japan, Korea, Mexico, Morocco, New Zealand, Norway, Republic of Turkey, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Thailand, United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay.	33.11	35.03	44.77
4	Argentina, Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Ireland, Jordan, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Portugal, Sweden, Tunisia.	2.58	2.55	4.76
5	Brazil, Czech Republic, Hungary, Islamic Republic of Iran, Kazakhstan.	4.16	4.16	9.98
6	Canada, Latvia, Russian Federation, Slovak Republic, Ukraine.	2.93	2.71	8.11
7	Denmark, South Africa, Belgium, Finland, Netherlands, Poland.	1.77	1.25	4.67
Total		86.34	94.84	97.50
Services				
1	Argentina, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Iceland, India, Indonesia, Israel, Italy, Japan, Luxembourg, Mexico, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Panama, Paraguay, People's Republic of China, Peru, Philippines, Portugal, Republic of Turkey, Romania, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay.	62.5	86.34	81.26
2	Brunei Darussalam, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Ethiopia, Honduras, Korea, Malaysia, Mauritius, Morocco, Nepal, Nicaragua, Republic of North Macedonia, Russian Federation, Tajikistan, Zimbabwe.	6.2	4.16	7.66
3	Azerbaijan, Hungary, Islamic Republic of Iran, Sudan, Ukraine.	2.5	0.8	2.86
4	Benin, Cameroon, Togo, Uganda.	1.3	0.09	0.47
Total		72.5	91.33	92.4
Industry				
1	Denmark, Ireland, Israel, Norway, Switzerland, United Kingdom.	5.32	5.06	1.28
2	Australia, Austria, Ecuador, France, Greece, Italy, Japan, Mexico, Panama, Peru, Philippines, Qatar, Uruguay.	7.21	12.31	7.30
3	Argentina, Bangladesh, Costa Rica, Cyprus, Korea, Morocco, Netherlands, New Zealand, Portugal, Spain, United States.	10.9	24.74	13.01
4	Belgium, Canada, Croatia, Egypt, Hungary, Indonesia, Iraq, Jordan, Luxembourg, Malaysia, Paraguay, Republic of Turkey, Sweden.	4.3	5.65	6.83
5	Albania, Azerbaijan, Brazil, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Honduras, Kingdom of Eswatini, Latvia, Mauritius, Plurinational State of Bolivia, Poland, Senegal, Thailand, Trinidad and Tobago.	2.83	3.67	4.95
6	Armenia, Colombia, Gabon, Islamic Republic of Iran, Myanmar, Nepal, Romania, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, United Republic of Tanzania, Vietnam.	4.65	3.63	5.48
7	Angola, Bulgaria, Cuba, Guyana, Iceland, Jamaica, People's Republic of China, Republic of North Macedonia, South Africa, Tajikistan, Zambia.	20.04	26.65	37.62

(continued on next page)

Table A.4 (continued).

Cluster	Countries	% Pop.	% GDP	% E.C.
8	Belarus, Chile, India, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Republic of Moldova, Russian Federation, Uganda, Uzbekistan.	22.03	5.89	14.81
Total		77.28	87.60	91.27
Manufacturing				
1	Bangladesh, Botswana, Democratic People's Republic of Korea, Denmark, Egypt, Ireland, Israel, Jamaica, Jordan, Kenya, Kingdom of Eswatini, Lebanon, Morocco, Myanmar, Oman, Paraguay, People's Republic of China, Peru, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Switzerland, United Arab Emirates, United Republic of Tanzania.	26.3	37.2	33.14
2	Algeria, Argentina, Armenia, Austria, Chile, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Indonesia, Islamic Republic of Iran, Italy, Japan, Korea, Mexico, New Zealand, Philippines, Republic of Turkey, Slovenia, Spain, Togo, Tunisia, United Kingdom, United States, Zimbabwe.	20.3	38.6	38.1
3	Australia, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Canada, Colombia, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Kuwait, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Pakistan, Portugal, Serbia, Slovak Republic, South Africa, Sweden, Thailand, Trinidad and Tobago.	7.2	6.5	7.4
4	Brazil, Finland, Iceland, India, Kazakhstan, Poland, Qatar, Republic of North Macedonia, Romania, Russian Federation.	23.9	7.3	15.94
Total		77.7	89.6	94.58

Table A.5

Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and asymptotic parameter *A* obtained from exponential fitting of energy intensity trajectories across clusters for the case of total (aggregated) sectors, and the four sectors analysed in this study.

Sector	Cluster	MAPE (%)	<i>A</i> (MJ/USD)
Total (aggregated)	1	26.22	0
	2	18.78	3.1
	3	18.59	0
	4	19.54	6.1
	5	27.25	14.8
	6	20.21	5.3
	7	19.15	7.3
	8	29.78	0
Agriculture	1	21.87	0.7
	2	27.14	1.7
	3	28.04	0.2
	4	17.17	4.2
	5	12.62	5.5
	6	20.2	0.1
	7	10.35	0
Services	1	39.1	0.5
	2	33.03	1.3
	3	28.73	2.1
	4	16.67	2.0
Industry	1	25.5	1.7
	2	16.96	0
	3	15.26	0.6
	4	18.05	1.8
	5	26.37	2.9
	6	32.42	0
	7	22.04	0
	8	15.61	0
Manufacturing	1	13.25	2.3
	2	28.13	4.8
	3	19.09	1E-3
	4	20.46	2.5E-3

reporting practices may affect comparability, particularly at finer levels of sectoral disaggregation. Sectoral coverage is not uniform across all countries and years, leading to variations in sample size between sectors. As a result, sector-specific clusters may not be directly comparable in terms of country composition. However, each sectoral analysis remains globally representative in aggregate terms, and the main conclusions regarding relative dynamics and saturation patterns are not driven by individual countries or outliers. In addition, the use of GDP expressed in constant U.S. dollars introduces sensitivity to the choice of base year and deflator. While this affects absolute energy-intensity levels, it has a limited impact on relative trends over time, which are the primary focus of the analysis.

Energy intensity is a composite indicator influenced by multiple factors beyond technical efficiency, including structural economic change, shifts in energy mix, outsourcing of energy-intensive activities, and changes in relative prices. As widely discussed in the literature, reductions in energy intensity do not necessarily imply proportional reductions in absolute energy consumption, particularly in the presence of rebound effects or rapid economic growth [14,35]. Accordingly, the energy-intensity baselines presented in this study should not be interpreted as direct proxies for energy efficiency improvements or emissions reductions. Rather, they provide a high-level metric for characterising the historical coupling between energy use and economic output. Their strategic value lies in identifying broad patterns, constraints, and divergences across countries and sectors, rather than in diagnosing specific drivers of change.

The empirical uncertainty envelopes constructed around the baseline trajectories represent the dispersion historically observed within country clusters. They do not constitute probabilistic confidence intervals and should not be interpreted as forecasts of future variability. In particular, the envelopes do not capture the potential effects of future policy shocks, disruptive technologies, or structural transformations that depart significantly from past experience. At the same time, the envelopes provide a robust and transparent representation of historically plausible ranges of energy-intensity trajectories. By grounding uncertainty in observed dispersion rather than in assumed probability distributions, they offer a pragmatic tool for benchmarking and scenario interpretation that is well suited to strategic analysis.

Despite these limitations, several features of the analysis support the robustness of the main findings. The use of long historical time series, broad global coverage, and consistent methodological treatment across sectors ensures that the results are not driven by short-term fluctuations or isolated cases. The convergence of insights across aggregate, country-level, and sectoral analyses further reinforces the validity of the overarching conclusions. Additional robustness checks on the sensitivity of the fitted trajectories to cluster composition are provided in supplementary material (S4). The framework presented here is not intended to replace detailed bottom-up modelling or policy-specific analysis. Instead, it complements such approaches by providing empirically grounded reference pathways that can be used to contextualise, benchmark, and stress-test alternative scenarios. Its applicability is therefore greatest in strategic planning, comparative analysis, and scenario interpretation contexts where transparency and empirical anchoring are of primary importance.

7. Conclusions and outlook

This study has developed a set of empirically grounded reference pathways for global and sectoral energy intensity based on the systematic analysis of historical data across more than 110 countries over the period 1990–2021. By combining data-driven clustering of country-level trajectories with transparent trend-based fitting, the analysis provides a coherent framework for characterising long-term patterns, heterogeneity, and limits in energy-intensity evolution. At the global level, the results confirm a sustained decline in energy intensity over recent decades, accompanied by a clear deceleration in the rate of

improvement. When extended as conditional baselines, these historical trends imply convergence towards energy-intensity levels that remain significantly above those assumed in many climate-aligned scenarios by mid-century. Importantly, this conclusion holds even when considering the most optimistic bounds of historically observed dispersion. Disaggregating the analysis by country clusters and economic sectors reveals substantial heterogeneity in both levels and dynamics. While some convergence is observed, particularly among initially high-intensity countries and sectors, historical trajectories consistently point towards gradual saturation rather than rapid, uniform improvement. Sectoral results further highlight that the scope for future energy-intensity reductions varies markedly across activities, with services and agriculture exhibiting early stabilisation and industry and manufacturing retaining greater — but still bounded — potential for improvement. A central contribution of this work lies in its strategic interpretation of historical evidence. Rather than offering forecasts or normative prescriptions, the cluster-based baselines and empirical uncertainty envelopes provide transparent reference ranges that clarify what past experience suggests is typical, exceptional, or unprecedented. In this way, the analysis supports more informed interpretation of long-term scenarios by making explicit the empirical distance between historically observed dynamics and the assumptions embedded in aspirational pathways. Rather than merely reporting historical trends, this study provides a novel diagnostic framework for the strategic assessment of energy transitions. The innovation lies in the systematic integration of temporal clustering with uncertainty benchmarking, offering a necessary empirical anchor for the next generation of climate-aligned energy demand scenarios. From a policy and modelling perspective, these findings underscore the value of empirical benchmarking in energy-demand analysis. Scenario pathways that imply sustained departures from historical baselines are not necessarily implausible, but they rely on assumptions about structural change, technological diffusion, or policy effectiveness that go beyond past experience. Making these assumptions explicit is essential for robust scenario design, risk assessment, and strategic planning.

Looking ahead, the framework presented here can be extended in several directions. Future work could integrate additional sectoral detail, explore alternative functional representations of long-term dynamics, or examine how specific policy interventions and technological shifts have historically altered energy-intensity trajectories within clusters. More broadly, combining empirically grounded baselines with prospective modelling approaches offers a promising avenue for bridging the gap between historical evidence and forward-looking scenario analysis.

In conclusion, by anchoring long-term energy-intensity pathways in observed data and explicitly characterising their dispersion and limits, this study contributes a transparent and reproducible reference framework for strategic energy analysis. Such empirically grounded perspectives are essential complements to normative modelling efforts as energy systems navigate the complex challenges of sustainability and transition.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jorge Manuel Barrios-Sánchez: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Ignacio de Blas:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Tommaso Brazzini:** Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Luis Javier Miguel-González:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

The authors used OpenAI tools to assist with language refinement and to improve the clarity of the presentation. All content generated with this tool was subsequently reviewed, revised, and validated by the authors, who take full responsibility for the final manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Data and statistics tables

This appendix contains the country groupings and statistical parameters that form the basis of the empirical energy-intensity pathways developed in this study. For a detailed discussion of cluster characteristics, methodological derivations of the exponential decline functions, and individual sectoral trend analysis, please refer to the Supplementary Materials.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2026.102197>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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